

RELAXATION OF THERMAL INDUCED INTERNAL STRESSES IN METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Internal strains and strain relaxation phenomena are studied using the neutron diffraction technique to monitor the evolution of elastic lattice strains. It is observed that residual strains relaxes both at elevated temperature and at room temperature (RT). By introducing the concept of a Thermal Strain Relaxation Loop (TSR-Loop), the observed internal strains are compared to theoretical predictions which do not include relaxation phenomena, and the discrepancy are discussed.

Keywords: internal stress, relaxation, neutron diffraction, Thermal Strain Relaxation Loop.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is well documented that the inherent mis-match of coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) in most metal matrix composites (MMC's) gives rise to internal stresses when changes in temperature occur. Theoretical predictions show that not only the local stresses around the inclusions, but also the mean stresses can reach relative high levels. The presence of internal stresses affect the mechanical properties of composites, hence relaxation of internal stresses in these materials are of great concern.

Previous investigations [1,2] have already focused on the relaxation of the thermally induced internal stresses in aluminum (Al) based composites reinforced with silicon carbide whiskers (SiC). The differences between these investigations and the present study are the matrix material, the volume fraction of whiskers and the technique of dispersing the whiskers in the matrix. The composite studied in [1,2] was based on the R400 powder with a natural surface layer of Al_2O_3 , which becomes a 1vol% dispersion of Al_2O_3 particles in the final material. The present matrix material contains 0.83wt% Al_2O_3 and contains 0.26wt% Fe and 0.18wt% Si. The main difference is, however, that the material studied here contains 10vol% SiC whiskers (Tokay β -type single crystals) as compared to the 5vol% composite in [1,2].

The whiskers are initially dispersed in isopropanol using high frequency ultrasonic energy. Afterwards they are separated from the alcohol by filtering and drying in vacuum at 180°C for 20 hours, and subsequently blended with the aluminum powder. After cold compaction and degassing at 450°C for 6 hours, the material is hot compacted and extruded at 500°C with an extrusion ratio of 15:1.

2. INITIAL STRAINS

In order to establish the level of initial thermally induced residual strains at room temp. 22°C, the lattice d-spacing in the extrusion (axial) direction of the unreinforced matrix material was compared to three measurements of that of the composite matrix. The results are given in table I.

Table I. 2θ for the Al_{111} reflection. Conversion into d-spacings is done using the applied neutron wavelength of 2.99376Å.

Sample	2θ [deg.]	d-spacing [Å]	matrix strain ϵ_m [$\times 10^{-6}$]	average ϵ_m [$\times 10^{-6}$]
unreinforced	79.511±0.004	2.34066	0	0
composite, #1	79.461±0.004	2.34189	525	507±100
composite, #2	79.473 ±0.004	2.34159	399	
composite, #3	79.454±0.004	2.34206	598	

From this table the reference double Bragg angle for the unreinforced matrix material is taken to be $2\theta_o^M=79.511^\circ$, and for the three tests of the composite, the average tensile strain relative to the free matrix ($2\theta_o^M$) was found to be 507×10^{-6} . A simple uniaxial conversion from strain to stress using a Young's modulus of 7×10^4 [MPa] gives a mean residual tensile stress of 35 [MPa] in the matrix. Using a Young's modulus of 3×10^5 [MPa] and a simple one dimensional stress balance condition, the initial mean strain in the SiC inclusions was found to be a compressive strain of -1065×10^{-6} . With the 22°C double Bragg angle of the SiC_{111} in the composite measured to be $2\theta=73.018^\circ$, the reference double Bragg angle for the free SiC whiskers was hence calculated to be $2\theta_o^I=72.928^\circ$.

3. THERMAL LATTICE EXPANSION

The lattice expansion was followed during an increase in temperature from 22°C to 300°C measuring the d-spacing over a period of approximately 7min. at selected temperatures. In figure 1 the thermally induced lattice expansion measured on the Al_{111} in the unreinforced matrix material (○) is shown together with two tests of the Al_{111} expansion in the composite (■ & Δ). The CTE of the Al_{111} in the unreinforced matrix material was found to be 25.8×10^{-6} [°C⁻¹] from a least square linear fit through the experimental data, which compares well with the typical text book average value of 25.3×10^{-6} [°C⁻¹] over the actual temperature range. This is indicating that despite the fact that this is a specific hkl-lattice expansion, its expansion resembles the macroscopic thermal expansion behavior of the material.

Uniaxial loading experiments have likewise verified that the Al_{111} lattice strain response to external loading, within the elastic regime, closely follows the macroscopic strain response of the matrix material [3], as expected due to the relative limited aluminum single crystal anisotropy.

Figure.1. Lattice expansion of: (○) Al₁₁₁ in the unreinforced matrix, and (■ & △) that of the A₁₁₁ in the matrix of the composite.

From figure 1 it is seen that the Al₁₁₁ in the composite appears to built up a tensile strain with temperature relative to the Al₁₁₁ in the unreinforced matrix material. However, with approximately 7min. measuring time to record a single lattice d-spacing, such a measurement obviously accumulate any possible relaxation of the lattice. Similar results reported in [1] for a 5vol% material is qualitatively in agreement with expectations from a continuum mechanics based analysis, whereas the present results for the 10vol% material clearly are in contradiction to these expectations. However, like observed here for the 10vol% material it has previously been observed in e.g. a Ti/SiC system, that composite materials can show an apparent CTE, which is higher than that of the unreinforced matrix material [4].

Figure.2. Mean strains in a 10vol% short fibre Al/SiC composite as a function of the temperature drop ΔT.

4. MODEL PREDICTIONS

The CTE of SiC was taken to be $3.9 \times 10^{-6} [^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}]$ [5]; a factor of 6 less than that of aluminum. Hence simple continuum based estimates of the thermal induced residual stresses and strains, indicate that a temperature increase of ΔT gives a compressive residual strain in the extrusion (axial) direction in the Al-matrix balanced by a tensile residual strain in the SiC-inclusions. One such model approach is based on the Eshelby equivalent inclusion theory [6,7], where the thermally induced mean matrix and inclusion strains due to a temperature change ΔT , can be calculated as described in [1]. The results for the present material are shown in figure 2 in terms of a temperature drop ΔT .

5. RELAXATION EXPERIMENTS

From the lattice expansion curves shown in figure 1 it was observed that the SiC inclusions did not appear to impose any dramatic constraint on the expansion of the Al-matrix. Contrarily the Al₁₁₁ in the matrix of the composite appeared to be promoted in its expansion as compared to the Al₁₁₁ in the unreinforced matrix material. It was subsequently decided to follow the development of the lattice expansion of the composite both at elevated temperature and at RT to further investigate this effect. The experimental procedure was to monitor the lattice d-spacing at RT, heat the sample in a furnace to the elevated temperature level quickly (in a few minutes), to follow the evolution of the d-spacing at temperature over some hours (6-10h), to cool the sample to RT as quickly as possible (with the sample sitting in the furnace this means within 15-20min.), and to follow the evolution of the d-spacing over a period of some hours at RT.

5.1. 200°C relaxation experiment

The lattice expansion of the Al₁₁₁ in the composite is given in figure 3 in terms of the double Bragg angle 2θ . The immediate expansion of the Al₁₁₁ lattice planes is seen from the initial drop in the double Bragg angle. The development of the d-spacing was subsequently followed over a period of 7.5 hours during which the lattice was seen to expand monotonically (the double Bragg angle decreases). Returning to RT the double Bragg angle is seen to increase corresponding to a drop in the d-spacing. During the holding time at RT the double Bragg angle is seen to increase slightly. There appears to be a trend towards limited relaxation of the tensile strain during the 9 hours holding time. However, the final value after approximately 9 hours is identical to that recorded immediately after RT was reached, and the variations are essentially within the experimental errors.

Figure.3. Development of the 2θ for the Al₁₁₁ reflection in the composite during the temperature cycle RT-200°C-RT.

5.2. 300°C relaxation experiment

The lattice expansion of the Al₁₁₁ in the composite is given in figure 4a in terms of the double Bragg angle 2θ . The changes observed in 2θ and hence in the d-spacings qualitatively follows those observed for the 200°C experiment. An experiment similar to the one described above was conducted monitoring the development of the SiC₁₁₁ lattice expansion. The results in terms of the double Bragg angles 2θ are given in figure 4b. Increasing the temperature to 300°C is seen to decrease the double Bragg angle corresponding to an increase in the SiC₁₁₁ d-spacing. This d-spacing appears to be essentially constant during the holding time at 300°C. Returning to RT increases the double Bragg angle corresponding to a drop in the d-spacing, and during the holding time at RT this d-spacing is observed to increase slightly.

Figure.4. Development of a) the 2θ for the Al_{111} reflection in the composite and b) the 2θ for the SiC_{111} reflection in the composite during the temperature cycle RT-300°C-RT.

6. DISCUSSION

The results of the relaxation experiments are discussed in the context of the theoretical thermal strains as calculated in section 4. From the initial strain level (labelled A in the following figures), the theoretical strain due to the temperature increase is added (with the correct sign) bringing the strain to the un-relaxed level for the actual temperature (B). At this temperature the experimentally observed relaxation is shown from the first data point of the holding time (C) to the last data point at the end of the holding time (D). From this level the theoretical strain due to a temperature reversal to RT is added bringing the strain to the un-relaxed strain level at RT (E). The first data point at the beginning of the RT holding time is shown as (F), and the last data point at the end of the holding time is shown as (G). This kind of display is here called a Thermal-Strain-Relaxation-Loop (TSR-Loop).

The results from the 200°C experiment is shown in figure 5. The RT double Bragg angle of the unreinforced matrix is $2\theta_0^M = 79.511^\circ$ and the initial tensile strain is $+507 \times 10^{-6}$ (A). From figure 2 the theoretical matrix strain due to a temperature change from RT to 200°C is -935×10^{-6} (sign is inverted relative to figure 2 as this figure is in terms of a drop ΔT), and following the solid line we hence find the theoretical un-relaxed matrix strain at the elevated temperature to be -428×10^{-6} (B). As observed from figure 1, then the unreinforced matrix showed a CTE of $25.8 \times 10^{-6} [^\circ C^{-1}]$ giving a total expansion of $+4592 \times 10^{-6}$ due to the 178°C temperature increase. The first data point of the composite expansion is at $2\theta = 79.079^\circ$, which relative to the $2\theta_0^M$ gives an expansion of $+4560 \times 10^{-6}$ and a strain of -32×10^{-6} (C). During the holding time at 200°C the double Bragg angle changes to $2\theta = 79.058^\circ$ and relative to $2\theta_0^M$ this corresponds to an expansion of $+4783 \times 10^{-6}$ and a strain of $+191 \times 10^{-6}$ (D). Similar to the above calculation of the un-relaxed matrix strain, we now follow the solid line on returning to RT

finding the un-relaxed matrix strain at RT equal to $+1126 \times 10^{-6}$ (E). The first data point at RT is at $2\theta=79.436^\circ$, which relative to $2\theta_0^M$ gives a strain of $+788 \times 10^{-6}$ (F), and during the holding time the double Bragg angle changes slightly to $2\theta=79.440^\circ$ giving a strain of $+746 \times 10^{-6}$ (G).

A number of results can be deduced from this graphical representation. It appears that the matrix strain due to the temperature increase does not reach the level at (B). However, as it takes approximately 2min. to reach the 200°C , and as the first data point is recorded over a period of 7min., then if the matrix has reached this level, the major part of this strain is relaxed within the first 9min. During the relaxation from (C) to (D) it appears that the matrix regains a small part of the initial tensile strain, though both levels (C & D) are very close to zero. Hence the matrix strain is nearly relaxed to zero during the 7 hours holding time at 200°C . On returning to RT the matrix strain is not observed to reach the un-relaxed strain level (E). Further during the 9 hours of RT holding time the relaxation from (F) to (G) is very limited, and it is in the direction towards the starting point (A).

Figure.5. Thermal Strain Relaxation Loop (TSR-Loop) of the composite matrix during the temperature cycle RT- 200°C -RT.

The matrix results from the 300°C experiment is shown in figure 6a. From figure 2 the theoretical matrix strain due to a temperature change from RT to 300°C is -1460×10^{-6} , and following the solid line we find the un-relaxed strain at 300°C to be -953×10^{-6} (B). Using the CTE of $25.8 \times 10^{-6} [^\circ\text{C}^{-1}]$ for the unreinforced matrix material we find a total expansion of $+7172 \times 10^{-6}$ due to the 278°C temperature increase. The first data point of the composite expansion is at $2\theta=78.735^\circ$, which relative to the $2\theta_0^M$ gives an expansion of $+8231 \times 10^{-6}$ and a strain of $+1059 \times 10^{-6}$ (C). During the holding time at 300°C the double Bragg angle changes to $2\theta=78.585^\circ$ which relative to $2\theta_0^M$ corresponds to an expansion of $+9843 \times 10^{-6}$ and a strain of $+2671 \times 10^{-6}$ (D). Similar to the above calculation of the un-relaxed strain, we now follow the solid line on returning to RT finding the un-relaxed strain level at RT equal to $+4131 \times 10^{-6}$ (E). The first data point at RT is at $2\theta=79.424^\circ$, which relative to $2\theta_0^M$ gives a strain of $+914 \times 10^{-6}$ (F), and during the holding time the double Bragg angle changes to $2\theta=79.441^\circ$ giving a strain of $+735 \times 10^{-6}$ (G).

The inclusion results from the 300°C experiment is shown in figure 6b. The reference RT double Bragg angle of the SiC is $2\theta_0^I=72.928^\circ$ corresponding to the initial compressive strain -1065×10^{-6} (A). From figure 2 the theoretical matrix strain due to a temperature change from RT to 300°C is $+2205 \times 10^{-6}$, and following the solid line we find the un-relaxed strain at 300°C to be $+1140 \times 10^{-6}$ (B). Using the SiC CTE of $3.9 \times 10^{-6} [^\circ\text{C}^{-1}]$, we find a total expansion of $+1084 \times 10^{-6}$ due to the 278°C temperature increase. The first data point is at $2\theta=72.795^\circ$, which relative to the $2\theta_0^I$ gives an

expansion of $+1574 \times 10^{-6}$ and a strain of $+490 \times 10^{-6}$ (C). During the holding time at 300°C the double Bragg angle changes to $2\theta=72.800^\circ$ and relative to $2\theta_0^I$ this corresponds to an expansion of $+1514 \times 10^{-6}$ and a strain of $+430 \times 10^{-6}$ (D). Similar to the above calculation of the un-relaxed strain, we now follow the solid line on returning to RT finding the un-relaxed strain at RT equal to -1775×10^{-6} (E). The first data point at RT is at $2\theta=73.035^\circ$, which relative to $2\theta_0^I$ gives a strain of -1262×10^{-6} (F), and during the holding time the double Bragg angle changes to $2\theta=73.025^\circ$ giving a strain of -1144×10^{-6} (G).

Where as the matrix TSR-Loop of the 200°C experiment (see figure 5) was in agreement with expectations, then the matrix TSR-Loop of the 300°C experiment is some what surprising. It is surprising to see that the first data point at 300°C (C) shows a matrix under a relative high tensile strain. Further this tensile strain increases during the holding time. Looking at the first data point on returning to RT (F), the strain is much lower than the calculated un-relaxed level (E), and only slightly higher than observed for the 200°C experiment. This is qualitatively in good agreement with the return from a higher temperature. During the holding time at RT this matrix strain relaxes to a level (G), which is essentially identical to the level observed for the 200°C experiment. The similarity is noticeable between the RT relaxation for the 200°C and 300°C experiment, compared to the differences observed at elevated temperature.

Figure.6. Thermal-Strain-Relaxation-Loop (TSR-Loop) of a) the composite matrix and b) composite inclusions during the temperature cycle RT- 300°C -RT.

Turning to the SiC inclusion TSR-Loop of the 300°C experiment (figure 6b) the situation is different. From the initial RT strain level at (A) it is observed that following the temperature increase the inclusions, as expected, moves into tension (C), though they do not appear to reach the un-relaxed

level at (B), and that this tensile strain is relaxed slightly during the holding time at 300°C (D). Returning to RT it is seen that the inclusions do not appear to reach the un-relaxed level at (E), but rather quickly relaxes to a numerically much lower level at (F). The fact that the relaxed matrix strain at the elevated temperature is of the same sign as the inclusion strain and hence the stress balance is most likely not fulfilled, further questions the high tensile strain observed in the matrix at 300°C. At present we can only speculate about the results for the matrix at 300°C.

Judging from previous hot tensile tests of the same material, the observations appear to reflect an unrealistic high level of elastic matrix strain at 300°C, which is not balanced by opposite strains in the inclusions. One explanation may be related to chemical reactions between Al and possible impurities, as it has e.g. been observed [4] that a reaction layer do alter the expansion behavior of the composite.

In summary it has been visualized how the concept of a TSR-Loop presents both the extremes of the un-relaxed strains and the experimentally determined relaxation sequences. The applied theory does not include any relaxation, and hence the shown TSR-Loop's are not predicted. However, relaxation is obviously important, and the simple theories for un-relaxed internal strains serve as bounds on the real strain levels. The results are in good agreement with expectations for the 200°C experiment and for the inclusion response during the 300°C experiment. The matrix response at 300°C is though difficult to explain.

The neutron diffraction technique has proven to be a unique probe for studying the mechanical behavior of MMC's, though it appears that the results can some times be at a level of detail, where it is difficult to correlate them with current MMC modelling based on continuum mechanics solely.

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